

A Suggested Training Module for Professional Foreign Language Competence

Valentina PANFILOVA¹, Aleksey PANFILOV²,
Irina SHESTITKO³, Marina SIRAEVA⁴

¹ Kazan Federal University, Elabuga, RUSSIA
v.panfilova2010@yandex.ru
ORCID: 0000-0001-6844-874X

² Kazan Federal University, Elabuga, RUSSIA
panfiloval@mail.ru
ORCID: 0000-0002-9652-6570

³ Belarusian State Pedagogical University, Minsk, BELARUS
irina.shestitko@mail.ru
ORCID: 0009-0005-8792-0444

⁴ Udmurt State University, Izhevsk, RUSSIA
marinasiraeva@mail.ru
ORCID: 0000-0001-9543-1724

Article information

Submission	05/02/2024	Revision received	03/03/2024
Acceptance	01/04/2024	Publication date	28/04/2024

Keywords:

Professional development, competence, reflexivity, training module, foreign language

Abstract: For this study, a training module is designed as an integral component of a professional educational program to include an educational workshop situated in a university classroom, educational research work, and a reflexive activity. A didactic model consisting of five structural and functional blocks, namely, normative-target, conceptual, substantive, technological, and effective-evaluative sub-modules were shared during the implementation stage. Results show that professional foreign language competence is a complex component of personal professional development as it has multidirectional components for the implementation of various speech and non-speech actions to achieve both certain personal and communicative goals.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Mesleki gelişim, yeterlik, özyansıtım, eğitim modülü, yabancı dil

Mesleki Yabancı Dil Yeterliği İçin Bir Eğitim Modülü Önerisi

Özet: Bu çalışmada bir üniversite sınıfında yer alan bir eğitim atölyesini, eğitimsel araştırma çalışmasını ve öz yansıtıcı bir alt modülü içeren bir mesleki eğitim programı tasarlanmış ve uygulanmıştır. Uygulama aşamasında normatif-hedef, kavramsal, maddi, teknolojik ve etkili-değerlendirici alt modüller olmak üzere beş yapısal ve işlevsel bloktan oluşan didaktik bir model paylaşılmıştır. Sonuçlar, mesleki yabancı dil yeterliliğinin hem belirli kişisel hem de iletişimsel hedeflere ulaşmak için çeşitli konuşma ve konuşma dışı eylemlerin uygulanmasında çok yönlü bileşenlere sahip olması nedeniyle kişisel mesleki gelişimin karmaşık bir bileşeni olduğunu göstermektedir.

To Cite This Article: Panfilova, V., Panfilov, A., Shestitko, I., & Siraeva, M. (2024). A suggested training module for professional foreign language competence. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 18(1), 99–111. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10987290>

1. Introduction

Modern teacher education faces critical challenges such as uncertainty, complexity, and diversity) as a high rate of change in teachers' competencies is in demand. Digitalization, data-based management, distance learning, personal-professional development, and networking are some keywords that signal the avalanche-like increase in the supply of educational services for children (Saenko et al., 2019; Taylor, 2022). Hence, the professional development of a future teacher should be combined with an understanding of the broad context of professional pedagogical activity. Implementing one's projects, working with different age groups, and motivating students are some of the roles and challenges of a teacher who organizes educational activities for students (Balbay, 2021; Otts et al., 2021; Krylova et al., 2020; Kilinc et al., 2023; Omodan & Addam, 2022).

The difficulty of mastering the teaching profession lies in the fact that in the process of mastering the educational program, a student must not only master the competencies provided for by the educational program mastered but also learn to transform them to meet the requirements of the Professional Teacher Standard (PTS) and due to the emerging changes in the school education system (Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation of October 18, 2013, No. 544n). Developers of educational programs must determine the necessary and sufficient list of competencies in demand in the new realities of school education and then determine the content of the subject and methodological training of a future teacher (Aubakirova et al., 2024; Orakova et al., 2024); Yilmaz & Arikan, 2019).

The two components of traditional training modules for teachers tend to focus on either solving general communication problems or solving professional-pedagogical problems. Within the framework of the labor function, a teacher must be able to perform the following labor actions: "The use of special language programs (including Russian as a foreign language), programs for improving language culture and developing skills multicultural communication" (hereinafter referred to as "LA 1"); "The use of foreign language information sources, translation tools, pronunciation jointly with students" (hereinafter referred to as "LA 2"); "Organization of academic competitions, conferences, tournaments of mathematical and linguistic games at school, etc." (hereinafter referred to as "LA 3") (Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation of October 18, 2013, No. 544n).

The wordings of LAs 1, 2, and 3 confirm the need for professionally oriented training in mastering the training module "Foreign language for solving professional-pedagogical problems" and require a rethinking of the technology of organizing the development of foreign language competence. Future subject teachers mastering the training module "Foreign Language" must know why they need knowledge and skills in a foreign language and how he/she will use them in personal and professional development. Within the framework of this approach, students' independent work will be of great importance (Adedokun & Oyetunde-Joshua, 2024; Arikan, 2004; Gabidullina et al., 2019; Kalimullina et al., 2021; Korableva et al., 2019). It is not only about volume – sufficient for mastering the system of knowledge and professional methods of activity in the course of self-education but also about the developed skills to independently set self-education tasks, increase the volume of the necessary information and dispose of unnecessary information, effectively use information for individual and group educational-professional purposes (Pogosyan, 2021a; Pogosyan, 2021b). The essence of independent work in mastering foreign language

competence today is an opportunity not just to overcome or smooth out various deficiencies (personalized and instrumental ones) but a systemic increment as a “skill of the future” (Ibraimova *et al.*, 2023; Kokorina *et al.*, 2023; Mashudi *et al.*, 2021; Minnegalieva *et al.*, 2020; Nurjamin *et al.*, 2023).

The problem of forming foreign language competence in the process of mastering educational programs of pedagogical education is sufficiently studied in modern pedagogical science (Artamonova, 2018; Bezukladnikov, 2017; Hawkins, 2007; Isaeva, 2012; MacKay, 2005; Morozova & Kostyukova, 2011; Sergeeva & Pokhodzei, 2014; Solonina, 2013; Timperley *et al.*, 2007; Zimnyaya, 2005). However, there is still no final definition of “foreign language competence” as such scientific discussion continues mainly because of several factors such as a complex and varied component composition, personal-subjective orientation, a variety of goals, and ranges of competence use (professional, scientific, technical, household spheres), and the complexities of foreign language communication. The variability of structural components in foreign language competence models is presented in Table 1 (Panfilova, 2015).

Table 1.

Component composition of the structure of foreign language competence

	J. Raven & N. Chomsky	Jan Van Ek	L. Bakhman	V.V. Safonova	I.I. Galimzyanova	A.S. Andrienko	E.G.Nikitina	A.I. Kurshepova	O.V. Galustyan	E.I. Baguzina
Linguistic	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Sociolinguistic	+	+	+					+		
Discursive		+	+			+		+	+	+
Strategic		+	+			+		+	+	+
Sociocultural		+		+		+	+	+	+	+
Pragmatic	+		+		+					+
Social		+								
Speech			+	+	+		+			
Compensatory							+			
Cognitive			+				+			
Information technology					+	+				
Personal						+				
Personalized										+

The practice-oriented development of foreign language competence emphasizes three major issues. First, the cognitive level involves mastering professional and linguistic knowledge. Second, the operational level includes the ability to continue professional communication in the professional sphere, and third, the personalized-professional level is manifested in having such professional-personal qualities as communication, tolerance, the ability to overcome the psychological barrier in foreign language communication, and the experience of professional foreign language communication. (Kostyukova & Morozova, 2011; Morozova, 2011; Nureeva *et al.*, 2019; Ofori-Kusi & Tachie, 2022; Zorba, 2023).

Mastering foreign language competence cannot be closed after mastering the training module “Foreign Language” of a specific educational program. Firstly, the openness of the personalized component of competence: mastering and improving knowledge of a foreign

language is a continuous process, which, subject to its relevance, continues at the level of educational-professional activities (Chong & Quek, 2022; Dube et al., 2023; Mbhiza, 2024). Secondly, the openness of the instrumental component of competence has its own content for various language users and is determined by predictable tasks of professional-pedagogical activity. In this regard, this study deliberately narrowed the concept of foreign language competence to the concept of professional foreign language competence (Dwomoh et al., 2023; Grigoryev et al., 2022; Karimova et al., 2023; Molomo, 2023). Professional foreign language competence is considered the ability to operate in a foreign language in the professional communication sphere and as a willingness to perform specific labor actions to use foreign language information sources, translation tools, and pronunciation.

Obviously, preparation for all forms of professional foreign language communication in the context of mastering the pedagogic education program seems rather complicated. It is necessary to acquaint a future subject teacher with the possible types and forms of using foreign language knowledge, abilities and skills, prolonging the process of mastering a foreign language in the form of independent work both on the process of mastering other training modules of the educational program and on the process of carrying out professional activities (Ivanova & Dimova-Severinova, 2021; Gazioğlu & Güner, 2021; Mdogana-Zide & Mafugu, 2023).

2. Methods

The context of this research involves the development of a didactic model of the training module for the formation of professional foreign language competence of students mastering non-linguistic programs of a pedagogy bachelor's degree. In organizing the mastering of the training module "Foreign Language", conditions are created for the formation of future subject teachers' readiness to perform the above labor actions and the ability to organize independent work of school children to use the target language for educational purposes. Modeling makes it possible to study objects of different natures to determine and clarify their already-existing or newly constructed characteristics – the main methodological idea of designing and testing a didactic model (Shchukin, 2008).

Understanding of the leading role of independent work in mastering professional foreign language competence by pedagogy bachelor led to the design and testing of a didactic model of the training module. The fundamental difference between the proposed didactic model of formation of professional foreign language competence in pedagogy bachelors of non-linguistic specializations when mastering the training module "Foreign Language" is that independent work and educational projects in the network university-school interaction become the leading forms of organizing students' educational-professional activities.

In this work, a dead-end administrative-didactic path is not used to reduce the number of classroom activities in favor of independent work. Searching for qualitatively new ways to activate independent work while filling it with personally and professionally significant (instrumental) content is necessary. Students' independent work in the training module has an enormous didactic and methodological capacity. Firstly, it is aimed at mastering the educational content of a problematic and professionally oriented nature, developing the ability to work with various types of information, developing analytical skills, controlling and planning study time, and working in a training team to solve educational-professional problems. Secondly, the experience of organizing the work of training teams can be easily transferred into professional activity and used in work with schoolchildren.

The leading approaches to the design and testing of the training module are the activity and research approaches. In the training module, a future teacher learns to solve typical educational-professional tasks, which consist of mastering the skills to organize schoolchildren's educational activities; this is the essence of the activity approach. A set of educational-professional tasks for students' independent work in the training module covers a labor action performed by a teacher in pedagogical activities: "The use of foreign language information sources, translation tools, pronunciation jointly with students". The research approach is understood as the formation of research competencies of a future teacher. The research competence of a teacher is the ability to use scientific-pedagogical tools to perform research work with children, and it covers the labor action: "Organization of academic competitions, conferences, tournaments of mathematical and linguistic games at school, etc." (Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation of October 18, 2013, No. 544n). When designing a didactic model for professional foreign language competence formation in future subject teachers, it is crucial to present the result and construct students' learning paths, understanding why each structural component of competence is needed.

3. Results and Discussion

Thus, the authors have attempted to design and test a didactic model for forming professional foreign language competence of pedagogy bachelors of non-linguistic specializations while mastering the training module "Foreign Language" (Panfilov *et al.*, 2017). The didactic model consists of hierarchically interrelated structural and functional blocks: regulatory-target, conceptual, content-related, technological and resulting-evaluative ones.

The regulatory-target block of the didactic model indicates the problem of ordering the training of a competent subject teacher with a sufficient level of formation of professional foreign language competence to perform specific labor actions. The training of such subject teachers is ensured mainly by designing the logical structure of the organization of independent work in the training module. The proposed didactic model is based on integrating approaches to teaching a foreign language: professional-contextual and personal-activity ones (see Figure 1).

The content-related block of the didactic model is a training module, "Foreign Language for Professional Purposes", considered a labor action formation unit (Margolis, 2017). The training module as an integral part of the educational program includes as follows: a training workshop (mastered in university lecture halls); educational research work (mastered in the network university-school interaction); a reflexive stage (conducted in university lecture halls) (Panova *et al.*, 2021). The training module starts with a motivating training event with mentors from network schools; completion of the training module occurs after the reflexive stage (determining the level of formation of professional foreign language competence and the degree of willingness to perform the above labor actions).

Structurally, the training module gives the answers to the following questions: 1) what abilities of a graduate will be developed after mastering the content of the training module; 2) what measurements should be used and in what way will it be found out that these abilities have reached that necessary level (minimum, optimal, advanced ones) at which one can judge his/her personal, social and professional readiness to perform certain labor actions.

Regulatory-target block		
Grounds: requirements of the Professional Teacher Standard for the performance of labor functions		
Goal: willingness to use professional foreign language competence for educational and professional purposes		
Conceptual block		
Approaches: methodology of the activity approach to modern education personnel training		
Principles: consistency, individualization, activity, responsibility		
Pedagogical conditions: motivational conditions, content-related conditions, participatory conditions, activity conditions		
Content-related block		
Invariant component of the training module		Variable component of the training module
Mastered by the entire training group		Flexible micromodules define individual learning paths within the training group
Technological block		
Methods	Forms	Means
Contextual-competence training Educational-professional pedagogical cases	Individual and group educational-professional projects in network interaction with educational organizations	Designing individual educational routes. Psychological and methodological support of individual educational routes.
Resulting-evaluative block		
Educational results: willingness to use professional foreign language competence for educational and professional purposes;		
the ability to perform certain labor actions and organize the independent work of school children to use the target language to achieve educational goals;		
capacity for reflection and subsequent transformation of professional foreign language competence components in independent work to solve educational-professional tasks.		
Evaluation criteria: formation of professional foreign language competence.		
Formation levels		
Minimum	Optimal	Advanced

Figure 1. Didactic model of the training module

The evaluation aims to determine the degree of correspondence of the level of professional foreign language competence among students to the level specified by the training module developers (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Evaluation of the formation of professional foreign language competence

The presented didactic model of the training module was tested in three stages: preliminary, implementation, and reflexive.

In the first stage, the relevance of the model design was determined. A survey of subject teachers (excluding foreign language teachers) of basic general education and secondary general education was conducted for a total of 125 people. The developed “Evaluation sheet for self-assessment of the professional activity of a teacher of basic and secondary general education on the basis of the Professional Teacher Standard” was used as a methodology (a three-point scale 0-2 was used). As a result of the data analysis, the sample of subject teachers was divided into two groups. The first group includes subject teachers actively performing LA 3 – 46 respondents. The second group includes subject teachers who do not perform or rarely perform LA 3 – 79 respondents. The average score (the degree of LA 2 implementation of the first group, “The use of foreign language information sources, translation tools, pronunciation jointly with students”) is 2 points. The average score of the second group is 0.7 points. The results obtained confirm the need to form professional foreign language competence in future subject teachers.

In conditions of high dynamics of changes in educational practice in terms of the demand for new competencies in the variable component of the training module, it is necessary to provide a quick setup and reconfiguration of flexible micromodule programs. In this case, the training module acts as a platform for forming an individual educational route within a training group. The flexible micromodule has the following elements: foreign language content to be mastered and projects (educational-professional pedagogical cases). This logic will increase the variability of learning paths while maintaining the volume of educational content.

The authors tested two individual educational routes (IER) types in the presented didactic model. “Basic Route” implies the absence of strict requirements for the basic components of professional foreign language competence, except for the “core” of the content of the “Foreign Language” program, coordinated with the subject area. In addition, a student chooses the volume and complexity of independent work with content as a backbone element of his/her route, independently forming the rest of the micromodule program according to his/her own personal and professional needs.

“Applied Route” is focused on specific professional-pedagogical tasks of schools in the network interaction between university and school and has more stringent requirements for the basic components of foreign language competence. The micromodule includes an obligatory element: distributed practice in educational organizations – network partners of the university. IER is available to those students who have expressed an interest in the school’s scientific-pedagogical projects and a desire to participate in developing and implementing joint research projects with school children of different ages. This IER will allow us to accumulate experience implementing LA 2 and LA 3 in forming professional foreign language competence.

At the didactic model implementation stage, the IER of training module students was determined by two types of diagnostic data: motivational and instrumental. Instrumental data: students in the 1st-2nd years of study were identified, demonstrating a high level of proficiency in a foreign language during the introductory testing, which was carried out using uncertified online tests (practice tests). Then, students’ self-report results were analyzed by filling in the “Maps for Assessing Students’ Foreign Language Competence” developed by the authors (Panfilova, 2016). Motivational data: Willingness/unwillingness to participate in

online training events at school was considered. The data obtained made it possible to identify a general trend in the IER for groups mastering the module “Foreign language for solving professional-pedagogical problems”. “Basic Route” was chosen by 2/3 of the students of the training group, while “Applied Route” was by 1/3 of the students of the training group. This ratio correlates with the data from the teachers’ survey.

Table 2.

Indicators and methods for assessing the components of professional foreign language competence

Component	Indicator	Assessment methods
Cognitive	A high level of professional knowledge (psychological-pedagogical, subject knowledge) and knowledge in the field of a foreign language, providing a successful orientation in professional-pedagogical tasks	Linguistic and communicative test tasks, expert assessment of a university teacher’s speech activity, expert assessment of a teacher-mentor of a network school
	Be able to communicate in a foreign language on professional-pedagogical topics in educational and professional conditions with students of basic general and secondary general education; work with scientific information in a foreign language, presented in different media; use digital tools (translation tools, independently work with foreign language Internet resources, etc.)	Analysis of the results of projects carried out in a training group and a network school, expert assessment of a university teacher’s speech activity, expert assessment of a teacher-mentor of a network school
Operational-efficient	Knows how to refer to his/her own experience of learning a foreign language; independently determine his/her educational route; evaluate the result of educational-professional activities.	Participant observation, expert assessment of a university teacher, expert assessment of a teacher-mentor of a network school, self-assessment of results

At the reflexive stage, the analysis of the obtained key educational results was carried out, and the level of formation of professional foreign language competence was determined. The study focused on the professional orientation of foreign language competence. Below are the significant components that determine the ability of a future specialist to solve typical problems using a foreign language arising in professional situations (LA 2): cognitive, operational-efficient, and reflexive ones. Indicators and methods for assessing the identified components of professional foreign language competence have been determined (Table 2).

The “raw” values of multi-step scales were converted into a single 100-point scale of standard T-points to carry out a comparative analysis of the data obtained using different diagnostic methods. The formation of structural components of professional foreign language competence differs at three levels of values: a minimum level (T=10-30), an optimal level (T=31-70), and an advanced level (T=71-100). Below is the diagnostic data of the results of students mastering the training module on the “basic” and “applied” routes upon the start and completion of the training module (see Table 3).

Data analysis allows the conclusion of the positive dynamics of forming all the declared components of professional foreign language competence. It has been found that based on activity-oriented pedagogical technologies and specially designed adaptive educational micromodules, the movement of educational-professional activities was set not only for the

development of universal competencies in the “Communication” category but for the ability to perform labor actions (LA 2 and LA 3) of future professional activities.

Table 3.

Levels of components of professional foreign language competence upon the start and completion of the training module

Expanding the training module	Levels of formation of structural elements of professional foreign language competence					
	Applied individual route			Basic individual route		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
Start of the training module	68.3	65	59	64	65.1	58
Completion of the training module	80.57	80.74	77.54	73.49	74.17	67.49

1. Cognitive component 2. Operational-efficient component 3. Reflexive component.

4. Conclusion

Professional foreign language competence as an integral part of foreign language competence is of both pedagogical and personal interest for a future specialist in school education. Mastering and, most importantly, using a foreign language in professional activities motivate personal and professional development and contribute to faster adaptation in an educational organization. Professional foreign language competence is a complex-component personalized formation; it has multidirectional components for implementing various speech and non-speech actions to achieve certain personal and communicative goals, as well as the goals of professional activity. Mastering professional foreign language competence is not a closed process since it continues independently after mastering the corresponding training module of a specific educational program. In the process of forming professional foreign language competence among future teachers of non-linguistic specializations with a certain time limit for mastering a foreign language, a limited amount of training sessions, as well as the observed diversity in the levels of basic knowledge of a foreign language, the most effective and optimized organization of their educational-professional activities in the training module is essential. The didactic model of the training module assumes the maximum increase in students’ activity; their inclusion in educational-professional tasks simulating the performance of future labor actions corresponds to students’ individual motives and abilities.

Thus, the presented didactic model makes it possible to form in future subject teachers of basic general education the willingness to use professional foreign language competence for personal and professional purposes, the ability to perform certain labor actions, to organize the independent work of school children to use the target language to achieve educational goals, the capacity for reflection and subsequent transformation of the components of professional foreign language competence in the process of independent work to solve educational-professional tasks.

Acknowledgements

Kazan Federal University Strategic Academic Leadership Program supports Valentina Panfilova and Aleksey Panfilov.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 12/02/2024).

References

- Adedokun, T., & Oyetunde-Joshua, F. (2024). Navigating the academic odyssey: Exploring the role of supervisors in supporting postgraduate students. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 7(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcve.2024.1>
- Arikan, A. (2004). Professional development programs and English language instructors: A critical-postmodern study. *Hacettepe University Journal of Education*, 27, 40–49. Retrieved from http://www.efdergi.hacettepe.edu.tr/shw_artcl-798.html
- Artamonova, Y. D., Vorobieva, O. V., & Demchuk, A. L. (2018). *Researcher of the XXI century: the formation of competencies in the system of higher education*. Moscow: Collective Monograph.
- Aubakirova, A., Kurmanbayuly, S., Akhmetova, T., Smailova, K., Koshanova, Z., & Bayekina, N. (2024). The effect of the use of contemporary technologies on teaching new terms in literature. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 15(1), 187–211. <https://jsser.org/index.php/jsser/article/view/5540/661>
- Balbay, S. (2021). Professional critical awareness development in preservice ELT students in spoken English classes. *Journal of Narrative and Language Studies*, 9(17), 289–305. Retrieved from <https://nalans.com/index.php/nalans/article/view/355>
- Bezukladnikov, K. E., Novoselov, M. N., & Kruse, B. A. (2017). Features of the formation of a foreign language professional communicative competence of a future teacher of a foreign language. *Language and Culture*, 38, 152–170.
- Chong, Y. S., & Quek, A. H. (2022). Navigating the contemporary rites of passage: A typology of STEM professional identity transition. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 7(3), 86–110. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2022.19>
- Dube, B., Mahlomaholo, S., Setlalentoa, W., & Tarman, B. (2023). Creating sustainable learning environments in the era of the posthuman: Towards borderless curriculum. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 5(1), i–x. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2023.1>
- Dwomoh, R. K., Osei-Tutu, A. A. Z., Oudghiri, S., Chhikara, A., Zhou, L., & Bell, T. (2023). Teaching emergent bilinguals: How in-service teachers' perception of first language acquisition theories inform practice. *Research in Educational Policy and Management*, 5(1), 33–52. <https://doi.org/10.46303/repam.2023.4>
- Gabidullina, F. I., Korganbekov, B. S., Makarova, V. F., Zakirov, R. A., & Kayumova, G. F. (2019). Concept “teacher” in language consciousness of students of philological faculty. *XLinguae*, 12(3), 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.18355/XL.2019.12.03.04>
- Gazioğlu, M., & Güner, B. (2021). Foreign language teachers' intercultural competence as a new aspect of professional development. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 4(2), 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcve.2021.3>
- Grigoryev, S. L., Saenko, N. R., Volkova, P. S., & Kortunov, V. V. (2022). Medial turn in education: Philosophy of understanding words and images. *Frontiers in Education*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.856616>
- Hawkins, E. W. (2007). *Modern languages in the curriculum*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ibraimova, L., Koyanbekova, S., Ryskulbek, D., Moldagali, B., & Serikova, S. (2023). Exploring national brands in the field of education: The case of Kazakhstan. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 14(2), 97–117. <https://jsser.org/index.php/jsser/article/view/4902/614>
- Isaeva, M. A. (2012). *Formation of foreign language competence of future managers in the university: Monograph*. Cheboksary: Pegas.

- Ivanova G., & Dimova-Severinova, D. M. (2021). The role of happiness in applying suggestopedia and fostering the language learning process. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 12(4), 365–383. Retrieved from <https://jsser.org/index.php/jsser/article/view/3564/544>
- Kalimullina, O., Tarman, B., & Stepanova, I. (2021). Education in the context of digitalization and culture: Evolution of the teacher's role, pre-pandemic overview. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 8(1), 226–238 <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/347>
- Karimova, B., Bazylova, B., Makasheva, A., Nurlanbekova, Y. & Ailauova, Z. (2023). Students' linguocultural competence: Insights from internationalization at home. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 14(4), 379–405. <https://jsser.org/index.php/jsser/article/view/5450/653>
- Kilinc, E., Tarman, B., & Yussupova, S. (2023). The association between college students' participation behavior and social media use. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 8(2), 55–67. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2023.11>
- Kokorina, Y. G., Khanbalaeva, S. N., Abdullayev, U. I., Vagabov, M. M. (2023). The concept of teaching archaeology by I. E. Zabelin. *Bylye Gody*, 18(2), 650–661. <https://doi.org/10.13187/bg.2023.2.650>
- Korableva, O., Durand, T., Kalimullina, O., & Stepanova, I. (2019). Studying user satisfaction with the MOOC platform interfaces using the example of coursera and open education platforms. Paper presented at the ACM International Conference Proceeding Series, 26–30. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3322134.3322139>
- Krylova, L. A., Zhundibayeva, A. K., Kadyrov, Z. T., Talaspaóeva, Z. S., Fatkiyeva, G. T., & Sabiyeva, Y. V. (2020). Portrait image in Pushkin's prose of the thirties in the 19th century. *Media Watch*, 11(4), 630–647. <https://doi.org/10.15655/mw/2020/v11i4/204630>
- MacKay, W. F. (2005). Language teaching analysis. London: Longman.
- Margolis, A. A. (2014). Requirements for the modernization of basic vocational educational programs for training pedagogical personnel in accordance with the professional standard of a teacher: Proposals for the implementation of an activity approach in training pedagogical personnel. *Psychological Science and Education*. 19(3), 105–126.
- Mashudi, M., Nurmansyah, A., Saenko, N., Nurjamin, A., & Sharifullina, S. (2021). The impact of English cultural awareness on Indonesian advanced EFL learners' grammar knowledge. *International Journal of Society, Culture & Language*, 10(1), 99–108.
- Mbhiza, H. W. (2024). Mathematics education lecturers' experiences of a virtual writing retreat and its impact on publication output. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 9(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2024.2>
- Mdodana-Zide, L., & Mafugu, T. (2023). An interventive collaborative scaffolded approach with a writing center on ESL students' academic writing. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 6(2), 34–50. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcve.2023.7>
- Minnegalieva, A. I., Mingazova, L. I., Ibrayeva, A. T., & Kayumova, G. F. (2020). Turkish world and literary relations of the East. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology*, 9, 2514–2520
- Molomo, P. A. (2023). Renewal in educational spaces as a relational aspect: Making way for a new culture of reasoning innovation and sustainability. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 5(1), 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2023.7>
- Morozova, A. L., & Kostyukova T. A. (2011). *Development of foreign language communicative competence of students of non-linguistic universities: Monograph*. Tomsk: Tomsk Polytechnic University.
- Nureeva, G. I., Khabutdinova, M. M., Mingazova, L. I., & Mashakovc, A. (2019). The system of genres in modern Tatar children's drama. *Journal of Research in Applied Linguistics*, 10, 993–1000.

- Nurjamin, A., Salazar-Espinoza, D.-E., Saenko, N., & Bina, E. (2023). Learner-oriented assessment matters: testing the effects of academic buoyancy, reflective thinking, and learner enjoyment in self-assessment and test-taking anxiety management of the EFL learners. *Language Testing in Asia*, 13(1), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-023-00247-z>
- Ofori-Kusi, D., & Tachie, S. A. (2022). Learning mathematics through WhatsApp groups in university preparatory program during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 7(1), 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2022.1>
- Omodan, B. I. & Addam, B. (2022). Analysis of transformational teaching as a philosophical foundation for effective classrooms. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 4(2), 15–29. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2022.9>
- Orakova, A., Nametkulova, F., Issayeva, G., Mukhambetzhanova, S., Galimzhanova, M., & Rezuanova, G. (2024). The relationships between pedagogical and technological competence and digital literacy level of teachers. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 6(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2024.2>
- Order of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Russian Federation of October 18, 2013, N 544n “On the approval of the professional standard” Teacher (pedagogical activity in the field of preschool, primary general, basic general, secondary general education) (educator, teacher) “(with amendments and additions). Retrieved from <https://base.garant.ru/70535556/>
- Otts, E. V., Panova, E. P., Lobanova, Y. V., Bocharnikova, N. V., Panfilova, V. M., & Panfilov, A. N. (2021). Modification of the role of a teacher under the conditions of distance learning. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(21), 219–225. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i21.25675>
- Panfilov, A., Panfilova, V., Ljdokova, G., & Kozinets, L. (2017). The educational program for transition from training to professional work. In R. Valeeva (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 3rd International Forum on Teacher Education (IFTE 2017)* (pp. 600–622). Kazan: European Proceedings. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2017.08.02.71>
- Panfilova, V. M. (2016). *Psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of foreign language competence of linguistically gifted students of a non-linguistic university*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Yelabuga.
- Panfilova, V. M., Panfilov, A. N., & Merzon, E. E. (2015). Organizational-pedagogical conditions to form the foreign competence in students with the features of linguistic giftedness. *International Education Studies*, 8(2), 176–185. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v8n2p176>
- Panova, E. P., Tjumentseva, E. V., Koroleva, I. A., Ibragimova, E. R., & Samusenkov, V. O. (2021). Organization of project work with the help of digital technologies in teaching Russian as a foreign language at the initial stage. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(22), 208–220. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i22.20573>
- Pogosyan, V. G. (2021a). Problem of innovations diffusion: A historical retrospective. *Voprosy Istorii*, 5(2), 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.31166/VoprosyIstorii202105Statyi30>
- Pogosyan, V. G. (2021b). Systemic approach in phenomenon research (a historiographic etude). *Voprosy Istorii*, 4(2), 253–265. <https://doi.org/10.31166/VoprosyIstorii202104Statyi62>
- Saenko, N., Voronkova, O., Volk, M., & Voroshilova, O. (2019). The social responsibility of a scientist: Philosophical aspect of contemporary discussions. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 10(3), 332–345.
- Sergeeva, N. N., & Hike, G. V. (2014). *Development of foreign language intercultural competence of students of non-linguistic specialties in the system of professionally oriented language education: Monograph*. Ural/Yekaterinburg.
- Shchukin, A. N. (2008). *Linguodidactic encyclopedic dictionary*. Astana: Keeper.

- Solonina, L. V. (2013). Basic principles of formation of foreign language educational competence. *Koncept*, 11, 36–40. Retrieved from <http://e-koncept.ru/2013/13220.htm>
- Taylor, B. D. (2022). A reductionist approach in curricular planning for teaching language arts. *Journal of Curriculum Studies Research*, 4(2), 30–43. <https://doi.org/10.46303/jcsr.2022.10>
- Timperley, H., Wilson, A., Barrar, H., & Fung, I. (2007). *Teacher professional learning and development*. New Zealand: Ministry of Education. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/education/school/48727127.pdf>
- Volkova, P. S., Orekhova, E. S., Saenko, N. R., Trofimova, L. V., & Barova, A. G. (2020). Features of the modern process of differentiation of sense and meaning in communication. *Media Watch*, 11(4), 679–689. <https://doi.org/10.15655/mw/2020/v11i4/204639>
- Yılmaz, M., & Arıkan, A. (2019). English language teachers' evaluation of an alternative professional development program. *Başkent University Journal of Education*, 6(1), 13–27. Retrieved from <https://buje.baskent.edu.tr/index.php/buje/article/view/116>
- Zimnyaya, I. A. (2005). *Key competencies as an effective target basis for a competency-based approach in education*. Moscow: Phoenix
- Zorba, M. G. (2023). Exploring novice English teachers' professional development: Insights from the Turkish context. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 15(1), 446–466. Retrieved from <https://ijci.globets.org/index.php/IJCI/article/view/1232/599>